

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract: *The article presents the study of the theoretical basis for the formation of qualities and attributes of primary school teachers through the study of scientific and pedagogical literature, examples of national and spiritual heritage and research in the field of pedagogical psychology. In addition, the psychological basis for the formation of qualities and attributes specific to primary school teachers is explained.*

Keywords: *elementary school, teacher, elementary school teacher, educational orientation, creativity, diligence.*

Introduction: The modern school requires innovative, socially active teachers who possess the qualities and qualities necessary for the personal and professional activity of a teacher. The historical experience of the most developed countries of the world shows that as they set out on the path to independence and development, they focused on upbringing and educating young people, and such a policy justified itself in historical experience. All educational work in schools is aimed at educating young people as harmoniously developed people. Humanism, democracy, respect for students are the main principles of state policy in the field of education in Uzbekistan[1]. That is why respecting the dignity of children, diligence in the child, love for the Fatherland, kindness to people and fostering a sense of compassion is a responsible and important task. This task is mainly performed by teachers of institutions of continuing education. Teachers-educators, who are called to bring up young people as moral, harmoniously developed people, must have a good knowledge of pedagogical ethics, pedagogical culture, rules of etiquette ... That is why the higher education institutions that train teachers have an important task - to educate future

teachers who will fulfill the principles of humanity, meet the highest spiritual and moral requirements, and acquire the qualities of pedagogical etiquette.

It should be noted that the research conducted by psychologists in our country has studied many aspects of the problems of professional training of future teachers, but the psychological basis for the formation of qualities and attributes of primary school teachers and an important mechanism for ensuring professional competence. The problem of the specific psychological features of pedagogical professional training has not been fully resolved. The above comments were the basis for our choice of the research topic "Psychological basis for the formation of qualities and attributes of primary school teachers."

Methods: The research includes E.I. Rogov's methodology "Assessment of the professional orientation of the teacher's personality" adapted to the national-territorial environment; Questionnaire "Study of professional and personal qualities of the future primary school teacher", theoretical analysis, observation, interviews, tests, organization of questionnaires, pedagogical and psychological research, mathematical statistics were used.

Results and Discussion: In order to impart modern knowledge, first of all, the coach must have such knowledge ". "However, simple logic requires that the most mature and experienced coaches be attached to the primary school, where the child's outlook, tastes and potential are formed". Accordingly, only the establishment of a conscious discipline inherent in the interaction between teacher and students in the educational process, the acquisition of knowledge and teaching students to think independently will have a positive impact on the formation of personality. At all stages of socio-historical development, the teacher's personality is revered as an example of the ethnic consciousness and thinking of a nation with a high social status. What should be the psychology of a modern primary school teacher who deserves such a high assessment, that is, his personal and professional qualities and qualities? According to current analyzes of psychology, education and upbringing is a national-ethnic phenomenon in terms of form, content and essence [5]. It reflects the rituals, traditions, customs and, in general, the ethnopsychology of its people (nation). Naturally, the ideal of each ethnos, that is, the nation, is realized in the education and upbringing of that nation. These paradigm-ideals embody the consciousness, views and values of this ethnos, the people, and the understanding of the national consciousness and national identity is reflected in the wisdom that the nation has gained over thousands of years of experience. It is known that the young generation that reads and is brought up always combines (assimilates) the ethnopsychological features of their nation [4]. These features include: self-awareness of the national consciousness, while retaining its

distinctive features and distinctive components; national thinking, the specificity of the thought process; the specificity of volitional-mental behaviors, actions, emotions, and feelings; the specificity of the national character in communication and interaction with other people, representatives of other ethnic groups. This requires the indirect manifestation of specific psychological features in the context of education and upbringing. Therefore, in carrying out the process of education and upbringing, the teacher must follow the following principles and laws: a) psychological and pedagogical influences on the student should be carried out through traditional activities on the basis of the principle of connection and harmony with the specifics of the nation, which are understandable to the pupil and are associated with the customs, traditions, traditions and ideals of this nation;

b) the generality of national consciousness and national identity psychological and pedagogical activity, the law of unity, in which the activity of the educator is highly optimal-rational, taking into account the nature of the national identity, moral and social values of the ethnic community (student). The complex (set) of absorption of psychological and pedagogical educational influences is organized in accordance with the evolution of moral, socio-legal and production, labor norms specific to this ethnic community; it is necessary to take into account the ability of students to adapt to certain psychological and pedagogical influences.

In line with these theoretical data, we used the questionnaire "Study of the professional and personal qualities of a future primary school teacher" to study the specifics of the study of the professional activity of primary school teachers. In the experimental phase of our study, the questionnaire "Study of the professional and personal qualities of the future primary school teacher" was developed using the criteria of pedagogues and psychologists on the most important qualities of a modern school teacher. Their analysis is discussed below. The color indicators of the attributes allocated for each item, the correlation relationship based on the frequency of the features are analyzed on the basis of the relationship of teachers and students involved in the training process.

Table 1

The results of the study of the importance of the formation of personal qualities of the future primary school teacher in the process of professional training

№	Qualities	Teachers		Students		t
		X	m	X	m	
1	Loyalty to his\her country, people, love for children	1,77	1,610	2,35	0,831	2,129
2	Practical and psychological literacy	2,67	1,30	2,82	1,78	0,438
3	Hardworking and creativity	2,45	1,41	3,25	1,8	-2,856**
4	Activity in public affairs	3,10	1,75	2,40	1,21	3,618***
5	Kindness, compassion, humanity	2,77	1,77	3,87	1,78	-3,376***
6	Humility, sincerity	3,02	1,83	3,30	1,82	-0,776
7	Perseverance, courage and a strong character	2,55	1,19	2,65	1,84	-0,344
8	Striving to consistently improve their knowledge and skills	3,97	2,16	2,67	1,40	3,134**

** $p \leq 0,01$; *** $p \leq 0,001$

Note: X is the arithmetic mean; m-standard deviation; t-student criterion

The results of the study by teachers and students of the importance of developing personal qualities in the process of professional training of primary school teachers show loyalty to their homeland, people, love for children; practical and psychological literacy; diligence and creativity; activity in public affairs; kindness, compassion, humanity; humility, sincerity; perseverance, courage and strong character; all of the qualities, such as striving to consistently improve their knowledge and skills, were noted by the subjects to have an average of three levels of importance on eight-level color performance.

The results show that prior to the analysis of the psychological indicators required for vocational training, it can be said that teachers and students were not mistaken in showing that personal qualities are important for vocational training. In this case, for teachers and students of primary school, the qualities of "loyalty to their country, people, love for children" (1.77 and 2.35), "practical and psychological literacy" (2.67 and 2.82); No differences were observed between the qualities of "humility, sincerity" (3.02 and 3.30), "determination, courage and resilience" (2.55 and 2.65). It can be said that teachers and students understood the importance of forming these personal qualities of primary school teachers in relative equality.

Teachers and students noted on the basis of color indicators that it is important for the personal qualities of the future primary school teacher to develop in the process

of professional training. Even when comparing these qualities in terms of color, we can say that the fact that "loyalty to one's country, people, love for children" reflects the same color index is a positive thing. However, they also assessed a number of personal qualities differently in statistical criteria: "diligence and creativity" (2.45 and 3.25); "Activity in public affairs" (3,10 and 2,40); "Kindness, compassion, humanity" (2.77 and 3.87); "Striving to consistently improve their knowledge and skills" (3.97 and 2.67) (see Table 2.1). Differences in teacher and student assessment of the importance of personal qualities required for an elementary school teacher were also reflected in their color and location indicators (Table 2).

Table 2

Personal qualities of the future primary school teacher a color indicator of the importance of formation in the process of vocational training

№	Qualities	Teacher		Student	
		Colour	Place	Colour	Place
1	Loyalty to his\her country, people, love for children	1,77	1	2,35	1
2	Practical and psychological literacy	2,67	4	2.82	5
3	Hardworking and creativity	2,45	2	3,25	6
4	Activity in public affairs	3,10	7	2,40	2
5	Kindness, compassion, humanity	2,77	5	3,87	8
6	Humility, sincerity	3,02	6	3,30	7
7	Perseverance, courage and a strong character	2,55	3	2,65	3
8	Striving to consistently improve their knowledge and skills	3,97	8	2,67	4

In this regard, teachers noted that it is more important to develop the following personal qualities on the basis of color: "loyalty to their country, people," love of children "(1); "Diligence and creativity" (2); "Determination, courage and resilience" (3); "Practical-psychological literacy" (4); "Kindness, compassion, humanity" (5); "Humility, sincerity" (6); "Activity in public affairs" (7); "Striving to consistently improve their knowledge and skills" (8). It is clear that teachers emphasize the importance of perfecting the humane qualities needed for a future primary school teacher, and then some professional qualities. In students, however, it looked different. According to them: "loyalty to one's country, people, love for children" (1); "Activity in public affairs" (2); "Determination, courage and resilience" (3); "Striving to consistently improve their knowledge and skills" (4); "Practical-psychological literacy" (5); "Diligence and creativity" (6); "Humility, sincerity" (7); "Kindness,

compassion, humanity” (8). From this, we can say that it is natural that there are similarities and differences in the imagination of the teacher and students in the development of personal qualities in the process of professional training of future primary school teachers. Table 2.2 shows the future primary school teacher’s "loyalty to the motherland, people, love for children", "practical and psychological literacy", "diligence and creativity", "activity in public affairs", "kindness, compassion, humanity", "humility, sincerity". It can be said that teachers tried to explain the importance of the formation of personal qualities in the process of professional training, such as "determination, courage and perseverance", "striving to consistently improve their knowledge and skills" on the basis of personal professional experience and students on the basis of imagination. It is in this way that we have focused on the interrelationships of qualities in the study of the importance of developing the personal qualities of the future primary school teacher in the process of professional training. Our next analysis is devoted to the interrelationships of traits.

In the correlation analysis, the attitudes of teachers and students to personal qualities were intercorrelated. On the basis of indicators, we can say that there are qualities that do not fully reflect the correlation between the relationship between teachers and students to the personal qualities of the future primary school teacher, but some are interdependent and inverse. The attitude of teachers to the qualities of "loyalty to their country, people, love for children" is the quality of "diligence and creativity" of students ($r = 0.351$; $p \leq 0.05$); Attitudes to the quality of "practical-psychological literacy" The quality of "diligence and creativity" of students ($r = 0.526$; $p \leq 0.01$); The attribute of "kindness, compassion, humanity" ($r = 0.476$; $p \leq 0.01$); A positive correlation with the attributes of "humility, sincerity" ($r = 0.674$; $p \leq 0.01$), and a negative correlation with the attribute of "striving to consistently improve their knowledge and skills" ($r = -0.380$; $p \leq 0.05$). In addition, teachers' assessments of "diligence and creativity" are inversely related to students' assessments of "practical-psychological literacy" ($r = -0.406$; $p \leq 0.01$) and "diligence and creativity" ($r = 0.430$; $p \leq 0.01$).), Can be seen to reflect a positive attitude with the assessment of the qualities of "humility, sincerity" ($r = 0.333$; $p \leq 0.05$) (Appendix 5). Similarly, a correlation relationship was encountered between the teacher and the students in fourteen more correlation coefficients. It can be seen that there is a partial interdependence in the perceptions and attitudes of teachers and students towards the formation of qualities in the professional training process of the primary school teacher, inverse feedback on a number of traits and interactions in the development of many qualities. The importance of the personal qualities of the primary school teacher will now be addressed in an analysis of the specific circumstances of the teacher-student relationship. Indicators of

the correlation between the development of personal qualities of teachers reflect the general picture (as well as the performance of teachers and students). The internal correlation in their relationship was also manifested in scattered correlation coefficients rather than in the whole positive relationship, and eight correlation relations were observed.

Their attitude to the development of the qualities of "loyalty to their country, people, love for children" is "determination, courage and resilience" ($r = 0.443$; $p \leq 0.01$); Attitude to the quality of "practical-psychological literacy" "striving to consistently improve their knowledge and skills" ($r = 0.413$; $p \leq 0.01$); Attitudes to the quality of "activity in public affairs" include "humility, sincerity" ($r = 0.423$; $p \leq 0.01$), "determination, courage and resilience" ($r = 0.475$; $p \leq 0.01$), self-knowledge and striving to gradually improve their skills" ($r = 0.400$; $p \leq 0.01$); Although we believe that the attitude to the quality of "humility, sincerity" reflects a positive correlation with such qualities as "striving to consistently improve their knowledge and skills" ($r = 0.485$; $p \leq 0.01$), but "diligence and creativity" humility, sincerity" ($r = -0.410$; $p \leq 0.01$); We can say that "kindness, compassion, humanity" and "determination, courage and steadfastness" ($r = -0.326$; $p \leq 0.05$) are negative (Appendix 6). Because all of the qualities listed are positive, it is also possible to recognize through simple observations that their importance in the process of professional training of a future primary school teacher is positively correlated with each other. This suggests that in the process of professional training, there are aspects that also clarify the attitude of educators to the formation of personal qualities in the training of primary school teachers. Perhaps the attitude of the students in this regard will create a special look. Nor can we note a positive point in terms of the correlational relationships in which students express the formation of personal qualities of the primary school teacher. In their indicators, too, few aspects of the interdependence of traits with sufficient and reasonable correlation were observed. The attitude of ordinary students to the qualities of "loyalty to their country, people, love for children" is characterized by "practical psychological literacy" ($r = -0.426$; $p \leq 0.01$) and "active in public affairs" ($r = -0.502$; $p \leq 0, 01$) with; The attitude of "diligence and creativity" is characterized by "aspiration to consistently improve their knowledge and skills" ($r = -0.354$; $p \leq 0.05$), and the quality of "humility, sincerity" is characterized by "determination, courage and resilience" (It is surprising in itself that it reflects a negative correlation with $r = -0.483$; $p \leq 0.01$). In fact, we can say that a positive connection between these qualities should be observed even in the natural and simple case.

There are also positive correlation coefficients in the attitude of students to the development of personal qualities, but they are not enough to combine the personal

qualities necessary for training and development: the quality of "practical psychological literacy", "activity in public affairs" ($r = 0.578$; $p \leq 0,01$) with the quality of "diligence and creativity" with the quality of kindness, generosity ($r = 0,563$; $p \leq 0,01$) with the quality of "humility, sincerity" ($r = 0,410$; $p \leq 0,01$); Positive connections were made with the qualities of "kindness, compassion, humanity" and "humility, sincerity" ($r = 0.432$; $p \leq 0.01$) (Appendix 7). A situation that represents personality traits is not enough to perfect a future elementary school teacher. A situation that reflects a sufficiently positive internal relationship between almost all of the above eight qualities can be said to be positive for the vocational training process. Otherwise the process is not enough in practice. The next analysis of the research results is devoted to the study of the relationship of teacher professional knowledge to the importance of the professional training process (Table 3). There are also different and distinct values in the performance of teachers and students in recording the attitudes expressed to the importance of professional knowledge for the professional training of a future primary school teacher. There were also differences in their values in terms of color and location. An important aspect of the research is that the criteria for assessing the place of professional knowledge in the professional training of future primary school teachers are equally important by teachers and students: deep understanding of the educational process, understanding its goals and objectives (1st place) ; mastering the basics of general psychology, pedagogical psychology and developmental psychology, ethnopsychology (2nd place); knowledge of the theoretical and practical foundations of modern pedagogy (3rd place). This means that teachers and students are equally aware of the importance of professional knowledge for the vocational training process. This means that students are benevolent in mastering the information provided by the teacher in the process of professional training.

Table 3

The results of a study of the importance of professional knowledge for the professional training of a future primary school teacher

№	Criteria	Teachers			Students			t
		X	m	place	X	m	place	
1.	Deep understanding of the essence of the process of education and upbringing, understanding its goals and objectives	1,33	0,47	1	1,38	0,49	1	-0,467
2.	Mastering the basics of general psychology, pedagogical psychology and developmental psychology, ethnopsychology	2,15	1,11	2	2,23	0,70	2	-0,362

3.	Knowledge of the theoretical and practical foundations of modern pedagogy	3,94	1,19	3	3,71	1,29	3	0,844
4.	Know the methods of teaching their subject	4,66	1,17	5	4,62	0,98	4	0,005
5.	Understanding the cognitive processes and psychological characteristics of school-age children, knowing effective ways to influence their personality	4,15	1,42	4	5,12	0,80	5	-5,254***
6.	To know the essence of educational work with parents and the community	5,53	0,68	6	5,12	0,92	5	2,515*

- $p \leq 0,05$; *** $p \leq 0,001$

It appears that students meet the requirements of the teacher with the ability to master professional knowledge. However, we see that there are some differences in their assessment of the methodological aspects of professional knowledge, the organization of activities and the importance of knowledge in human psychology. Teachers are in 5th place and students are in 4th place in terms of teaching their subject; understanding of cognitive processes and psychological characteristics of school-age children, knowledge of effective ways to influence their personality, teachers in 4th place, students in 5th place; Knowledge of the content of educational work with parents and the community was rated by teachers in 6th place and students in 5th place. It is obvious that in the process of professional training, teachers have a deeper knowledge of child psychology, which helps them to teach their subject, and, in turn, to know the content of educational work with parents and the community. In students, the knowledge in this area was assessed with the same 5th place. From the statistical differences in the color frequencies of the results, it is also shown that the differences between them are expressed in terms of reliability. To understand the cognitive processes and psychological characteristics of school-age children, to know effective ways to influence their personality (4,15 and 5,12; $t = -5,254$, $p \leq 0,001$); to know the content of educational work with parents and the community (5.53 and 5.12; $t = 2.515$, $p \leq 0.05$). If the professional knowledge of teachers and students in the process of professional training allows to establish a broader and more positive system of "subject-subject", "teacher-student" relationship in the educational environment to achieve consistency in the relationship between the remaining criteria. Continuing the analysis, let us refer to the correlation dependence on the reported relationship to occupational knowledge (Appendix 8). In this analysis, as in the correlation of personality traits, the relationship between teacher and students in the process of professional training, the importance of internal knowledge between the criteria did not

reflect a wide range of positive correlations, but the correlation coefficients of positive and negative values were sufficiently reflected. The attitude of teachers to the criterion "deep understanding of the essence of the process of education and upbringing, understanding its goals and objectives", the criterion "knowledge of the methodology of teaching their subject" ($r = 0.467$; $p \leq 0.01$) and to know the essence of the work "($r = 0.498$; $p \leq 0.01$); The criterion "knowledge of the theoretical and practical foundations of modern pedagogy" is the criterion "understanding the cognitive processes and psychological characteristics of school-age children, knowledge of effective ways to influence their personality" ($r = 0.449$; $p \leq 0.01$); "Understanding of cognitive processes and psychological characteristics of school-age children, knowledge of effective ways to influence their personality" ($r = 0.577$; $p \leq 0.01$) and "knowledge of methods of teaching their subject" and Criterion "knowledge of the content of educational work" ($r = 0.573$; $p \leq 0.01$); The criterion of "understanding the cognitive processes and psychological characteristics of school-age children, knowing effective ways to influence their personality" is the criterion "knowledge of the theoretical and practical foundations of modern pedagogy" ($r = 0.708$; $p \leq 0.01$), and understanding of psychological features, knowledge of effective ways to influence their personality "($r = 0.582$; $p \leq 0.01$), criterion "knowledge of the content of educational work with parents and the community" ($r = 0.665$; $p \leq 0.01$) is commendable. At the same time, negative correlations were also observed between the attitudes of teachers and students towards professional knowledge. For example, the criterion "deep understanding of the essence of the process of education and upbringing, understanding its goals and objectives" with the criterion "mastering the basics of general psychology, pedagogical psychology and developmental psychology, ethnopsychology" ($r = -0.547$; $p \leq 0.01$); Criteria "general psychology, pedagogical psychology and developmental psychology, mastering the basics of ethnopsychology" with the criteria "knowledge of the theoretical and practical foundations of modern pedagogy" ($r = -0.443$; $p \leq 0.01$) -0,505; $p \leq 0,01$) and a number of other cases. Of course, the role of professional knowledge is always recognized, but it is desirable that their importance for the professional activity of primary school teachers is reflected in a positive attitude. Perhaps the specific nature of the results allows us to obtain other information. Looking at the results of the study, the correlation coefficients, which reflect the attitude of teachers to the importance of professional knowledge in the work of the future primary school teacher, indicate that much needs to be done in this regard. Negative attitudes are more prevalent than positive interdependencies in teachers' attitudes: "deep understanding of the essence of the educational process, its goals and objectives", "general psychology, pedagogical psychology and developmental psychology, the basics of ethnopsychology". between

the criteria "knowledge of the practical basis" ($r = -0.371$; $p \leq 0.01$) and "understanding the cognitive processes and psychological characteristics of school-age children, knowledge of effective ways to influence their personality" ($r = -0.331$; $p \leq 0.01$) links are a clear example. If the above shortcomings are eliminated in the process of professional training of future primary school teachers, it will undoubtedly serve to effectively organize the activities of teachers. We cannot also say that the results of important indicators of professional knowledge for the professional training of future primary school teachers are positive enough. It is safe to say that they replaced the knowledge of the profession in their primary school teachers in a way that suited their teachers. There are positive correlation coefficients in students' attitudes, but they are few: "knowledge of the methodology of teaching their subject" with the criterion "deep understanding of the essence of the educational process, understanding its goals and objectives" ($r = 0.403$; $p \leq 0.01$); The criterion "knowledge of the theoretical and practical foundations of modern pedagogy" and "knowledge of the content of educational work with parents and the community" ($r = 0.412$; $p \leq 0.01$) had a positive correlation coefficient. The remaining significant coefficients are negative. This is unfortunate. In the process of professional training of future primary school teachers, if the professional knowledge, personal and professional qualities necessary for a modern educator are combined, in the future the teacher will be able to use it wisely in their professional activities. In the process of professional training of future primary school teachers, it is necessary to pay attention to ensuring sufficient internal connection of professional knowledge.

Conclusion. Modern education places high demands on the professional training of primary school teachers and their personal and professional maturity (psychology): effective adaptation of modern primary school teachers to professional activity, perfect adherence to modern teaching methods, strict adherence to current principles of education, modern The professional knowledge required for a teacher is determined by the fact that he / she combines personal and professional qualities and uses them rationally in his / her professional activity. In the process of professional training of future primary school teachers, the set of psychological and pedagogical educational influences that a teacher should have should be consistent with the evolution of ethical, socio-legal and production norms of this ethnic community and take into account the ability of students to adapt to these psychological and pedagogical influences.

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